

THE FATTY OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *SOLANUM INDICUM*, LINN.

BY S. V. PUNTAMBEKAR AND S. KRISHNA.

The oil from the seeds of *Solanum indicum*, Linn. consists of the glycerides of lauric, palmitic, stearic, arachidic, oleic and linoleic acids together with the phytosterols, sitoaterol and carpesterol, and a hydrocarbon of high molecular weight and of m.p. 66-67°

Solanum indicum, Linn. (N.O. *Solanaceae*) known as Vrihati in Sanskrit and Birhatta in Hindi is a much branched under-shrub found throughout India and is particularly plentiful in the forests of Madras Province. The plant is an important drug of the Ayurvedic system of medicine, its roots being included among the ten important roots (dasamula) used for bronchitis, asthma and difficult parturition (Watt, "Dictionary of the Economic Products of India", Vol. VI, IIIA, p. 258). The fruit is a berry 0.3—0.35" in diameter, yellow when ripe and contains several small seeds which yield a yellowish orange fatty oil. The oil is also considered to possess medicinal properties.

A few physical and chemical constants of the fatty oils from the seeds of the allied species *S. melongena*, Linn., *S. mammosum*, Linn., *S. surinamense*, Steud (*Olien und Vetten*, 1919, 4, 417) and *S. lycopersicum* (Jemieson and Bailey, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1919, 11, 850; Rabak, *Chem. News*, 1917, 117, 100) have been previously recorded. But only recently the fatty oils obtained from the seeds of *S. xanthocarpum*, Schrad and Wendle (Gupta and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 367) and from the seeds of *S. nigrum*, Linn. (Pendse, *ibid.*, 1937, 14, 367) have been examined in some detail and shown to consist of the glycerides of palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids. Our examination of the fatty oil from the seeds of *S. indicum* Linn., the results of which are recorded below, has shown that besides the glycerides mentioned above, the oil contains small percentages of the glycerides of lauric and arachidic acids.

EXPERIMENTAL

The air-dried berries of *S. indicum* were received from the Divisional Forest Officer, Lansdowne Forest Division, Lansdowne, U.P., and were found to consist of 35% fruit shell and 65% seeds. The powdered seeds on extraction with petroleum ether yielded 10.1% of a pale yellow fatty oil having the constants recorded in Table I.

TABLE I.
Chemical and physical constants.

FATTY OIL.					
Consistency	...	Thin	Sap. value	...	177.6
Rotation $[\alpha]_D^{25}$	...	+0.5	Acid value	...	17.8
			Acetyl value	...	44.4
Sp. gr. at 15.5°	...	0.9156	Unsaponifiable matter	...	2%
Refrac. index at 15.5°	...	1.4671			
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	121.5			
MIXED ACIDS,					
Mean M.W.	...	293.1	Saturated acids	...	15.5%
Iodine value (Hanus)	...	123.0	Unsaturated acids	...	84.5%

{ Carpestrol, 0.15%
Residual matter, 1.8%

Composition of the Mixed Fatty Acids

The oil (200 g.) was saponified with alcoholic sodium hydroxide. After distilling off the alcohol the resultant soap was dissolved in water and the mixed acids liberated by the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The acids were washed with warm water and neutralised with 10% sodium hydroxide. The soap solution was concentrated by evaporation on a water-bath, incorporated with washed filter paper pulp and the resulting mass was dried, powdered and extracted with ether in a Soxhlet to remove the unsaponifiable matter. The mixed acids (142 g.) were liberated from the residual soap, purified in the usual manner and were separated into solid and liquid acids by the well known Twitchell's lead salt-alcohol method (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

Acids,	Net weight-
(S) Solid	23 g.
(S') Solid	1.2
(L) Liquid	117.8

Solid Acids (S).

The solid acids (23 g.) were converted into methyl esters in the usual manner with 3% methyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid. After distilling off methyl alcohol the esters were washed with saturated salt solution, 5% sodium carbonate and finally with distilled water. After drying under vacuum 23 g. of the esters were distilled at 6 mm. into the following fractions (TABLE II).

TABLE II.

Fractions.	B.p.	Mean M.W.	Net wt.	Component methyl esters			
				Laurate.	Palmitate.	Stearate.	Arachidate.
S ₁	up to 175°	248·7	1·90 g	0·72	1·18	...	...
S ₂	175-180°	274·4	2·18	...	1·84	0·34	...
S ₃	180-185°	275·7	4·06	...	3·23	0·83	...
S ₄	185-187°	285·9	5·12	...	2·21	2·91	...
S ₅	187-192°	289·9	3·14	...	0·91	2·23	...
S ₆	192-205°	304·6	1·80	...	...	1·38	0·42
Residue	...	Unpolymerised	2·00	...	...	1·00	1·00
			Polymerised*	1·94	...	...	...
Loss	...	...	0·86	...	...	...	...
Total	...	...	23·00	0·72	9·37	8·69	1·42

% Esters un-
polymerised and
distilled (20·2g.)

... 100·00 3·57 46·30 43·00 7·04

All these fractions were separately saponified, the corresponding acids were liberated and these were fractionally crystallised from acetone to isolate the individual acids in the usual manner.

Acids from fraction S₁ had a mean M.W. of 234·7. On twice crystallising from dilute acetone a product melting at 59-61° (Mean M.W. 258) was obtained. Mixed with pure palmitic acid, the m.p. was raised to 61-62°. The fraction, therefore, appeared mostly to consist of palmitic with some lauric acid. That it contained lauric acid is proved by the fact that this acid has been isolated from solid acids (S') as described later.

Acids from fractions S₂, S₃, S₄ and S₅ were separately obtained and fractionally crystallised from acetone. They were found to consist of palmitic and stearic acids. Fractions S₂ and S₃, on crystallisation, yielded almost pure palmitic acid (m.p., 61-62°, M.W. 258·4), whereas fractions S₄ and S₅ gave mixtures of palmitic and stearic acids (m.p., 54-55°, M.W. 271·9 and m.p. 53-54°, M.W. 275·9). As the melting points and the mean molecular weights of these two fractions were nearly approaching those of an eutectic mixture (m.p. 54-55°, M.W. 270) of palmitic and stearic acids, it was difficult to separate these acids for identification. Their presence

* This is due to the polymerisation of the small amount of unsaturated acid esters (Iodine value of saturated acid ester, 2·3) at elevated temperature of distillation.

was, however, assumed on account of the finding of palmitic acid in fraction S_3 and stearic acid in fraction S_6 .

The acids from fraction S_6 on crystallisation gave a product melting at 66-67° (M.W. 289·8). Its mixed melting point with pure stearic acid was 65-66°. The product obtained from mother-liquor melted at 63-65° (M.W. 299·3). This showed the crystallised acid to be almost pure stearic acid and that the small amount of the higher fatty acid (arachidic acid which has been isolated and identified from the residual esters) present in the fraction got relatively concentrated in the mother-liquor product thereby increasing its M.W. and lowering its m.p.

The acids from the residual esters were dark in colour, soluble in alcohol but only partially soluble in acetone and petroleum ether. They were, therefore, thoroughly extracted with petroleum ether which separated the fatty acids from the resinous matter. The petroleum ether extract on distillation of the solvent was twice crystallised from acetone when minute needles, melting at 76-77° (M.W. 308·2), were obtained. The acid is apparently arachidic but on account of the absence of a pure sample of the acid and of insufficiency of the material further identification was not possible. The acids obtained from the acetone mother-liquor had the mean M.W. 291 and were evidently mixtures of arachidic and stearic acids.

Solid Acids (S').

These acids were liberated from the lead salts crystallising out from the lead salts of liquid acids on standing after their separation by Twitchell's method. They melted at 36° and had the mean M.W. of 213·6. Recrystallised from dilute acetone they melted at 40-41° (M.W. 204). Mixed melting point with pure lauric acid remained unchanged indicating the portion to be lauric acid. The acids, therefore, contain mainly lauric acid mixed with a small amount of liquid acids.

Liquid Acids (L).

Oxidation.—The liquid acids were saponified to break up any ethyl esters which might have been formed during Twitchell's separation. A portion of the de-esterified acids was converted into potassium soap and oxidised in cold alkaline solution with dilute potassium permanganate according to the modified method of Hazura (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology and Analysis of Oils, Fats and Waxes", 6th Ed., Vol. I, p. 575). From the precipitated oxidised acids dihydroxystearic acid, m.p. 131-32°, M.W. 316·2 and a tetrahydroxystearic acid, m.p. 156-58°, M.W. 349, were isolated. The filtrate yielded azeleic acid, m.p. 101-02°, M.W. 186. No hexahydroxystearic acid was found indicating thereby the absence of linolenic acid.

Bromination—Freshly prepared mixed fatty acids (2·1102 g.), from which unsaponifiable matter was removed, were brominated according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler (Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.*, p. 585) yielding 3·7230 g. of the brominated product but no hexa or higher bromides. Crystallised from petroleum ether the brominated product gave white needles of tetrabromostearic acid (m.p. 113-14°. M. W. 598), the mixed melting point of which with a pure sample of tetrabromo stearic acid remained unaltered. The oxidation and the bromination results thus clearly showed that the liquid acids consisted only of oleic and linoleic acids.

The above data on calculation gave the percentages of the constituent acids as follows:—Lauric (0·6%), palmitic (7·2%), stearic (6·6%), arachidic (1·1%), oleic (35·0%) and linoleic (49·5%).

Unsaponifiable Matter.

The unsaponifiable matter obtained from the sodium soaps of the mixed acids by extraction with ethyl ether, when crystallised from cold alcohol, gave a product melting at 65-66°. This when recrystallised from alcohol melted at 66°-67°. It was not soluble in cold concentrated sulphuric acid, nor was it coloured by the contact of that acid indicating thereby that it was a hydrocarbon. The amount of the hydrocarbon being very small its further identification was not possible.

The mother-liquor from above was concentrated and allowed to crystallise in cold when a product, m.p. 124-25°, separated out. On recrystallisation from alcohol (95%) it melted at 131-32° and its acetyl derivative at 120-21°. The product gave the usual tests for sterols and, therefore, appears to be a mixture of two or more phytosterols at least one of which is the common one, sitosterol, found in vegetable oils.

Carpesterol.

After standing for some days a white flocculent matter, partly suspended and partly settled down, was found in the oil. This was filtered off and crystallised from 95% alcohol forming star-shaped aggregates, m.p. 242-43°.

The substance is insoluble in acid and in alkali and its elementary analysis shows absence of nitrogen and sulphur. It is not affected by boiling with alcoholic potassium hydroxide. Its alcoholic solution does not develop any colour with ferric chloride. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour which on standing turns deep orange and gives the other characteristic colour reactions of a sterol. The substance, therefore, appears to be a sterol.

* Liquid acids at this stage were found to have undergone polymerisation and were, therefore, not taken for bromination study.

The acetyl derivative of the above substance was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from alcohol, when needles, m.p. 192°, were obtained. The substance, therefore, appears to be the sterol, carpesterol (m.p. 248°; acetyl derivative, m.p. 194°) isolated by Saiyed and Kanga (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 4A, 255) and by Gupta and Dutt (*J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 95), from the fatty oil of the seeds of *S. xanthocarpum*, Schrad and Wendle.

DISCUSSION.

Although there is a fair amount of agreement between the characteristics and the constituents of the fatty oils of the seeds of *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. indicum*, yet a few points of difference may be pointed out. Whereas there is no other satisfactory explanation to offer for the divergence in rotation, specific gravity and unsaponifiable matter content, except the possible inherent physiological difference in the two species, the strikingly high acid value of the *S. xanthocarpum* oil, the high mean molecular-weight of its mixed acids (322.7) and the difference in their oleic (42.93%) and linoleic (36.18%) acid percentages may be regarded as due to the polymerised and oxidised state of the oil used in their investigation by Gupta and Dutt. This fact, we think, is sufficiently proved by the comparison of the iodine value of the mixed acids (121.37) as reported by these workers and as computed (103.76) by us from their figures for percentages of the constituent acids.

The characteristics of the fatty oil of another allied *Indica* spp., *S. nigrum*, reported by Pendse (*loc. cit.*) show that the nature of this oil is appreciably different from that of *S. xanthocarpum* and *S. indicum* oils. All these three oils may, however, be put in the semi-drying class occupying places nearer to the drying than to the non-drying limits.